

Additional file 10. Pyrolysis GC-MS analysis of ball milled wood (BMW), different LCC fractions, and the residue.

Fraction	Line	C	G	S	H	P	L	S/G	C/L
BMW	WT	78.1 ±	7.72 ±	11.80 ±	1.24 ±	0.08 ±	20.8 ±	1.53 ±	3.75 ±
		0.5	0.14	0.08	0.29	0.00	0.4	0.03	0.09
	TR	79.1 ±	7.81 ±	10.63 ±	1.41 ±	0.07 ±	19.9 ±	1.36 ±	3.97 ±
		0.4	0.21	0.27	0.12	0.01	0.4	0.02***	0.09*
LCC-X	WT	91.1 ±	2.79 ±	3.72 ±	1.34 ±	0.08 ±	7.9 ± 0.2	1.33 ±	11.50 ±
		0.2	0.05	0.03	0.11	0.01		0.02	0.26
	TR	91.2 ±	3.01 ±	3.65 ±	1.24 ±	0.08 ±	8.0 ±	1.21 ±	11.42 ±
		0.1	0.02***	0.11	0.10	0.01	0.1	0.03**	0.22
LCC-1	WT	79.6 ±	7.26 ±	9.06 ±	2.39 ±	0.18 ±	18.9 ±	1.25 ±	4.21 ±
		0.7	0.44	0.23	0.05	0.00	0.6	0.04	0.17
	TR	75.2 ±	8.51 ±	11.46 ±	2.75 ±	0.20 ±	22.9 ±	1.35 ±	3.29 ±
		0.5***	0.25**	0.22***	0.08**	0.02	0.5***	0.01**	0.10***
LCC-2	WT	57.5 ±	11.58 ±	17.23 ±	1.96 ±	0.06 ±	30.8 ±	1.49 ±	1.86 ±
		0.6	0.17	0.12	0.05	0.01	0.3	0.01	0.03
	TR	59.6 ±	11.92 ±	15.85 ±	2.05 ±	0.08 ±	29.9 ±	1.33 ±	2.00 ±
		1.0*	0.73	0.78*	0.30	0.00	1.3	0.04**	0.09
LCC-3	WT	51.1 ±	14.36 ±	23.37 ±	2.83 ±	0.25 ±	40.8 ±	1.63 ±	1.25 ±
		0.4	0.49	0.35	0.14	0.01	0.7	0.03	0.01
	TR	53.1 ±	14.05 ±	21.63 ±	2.69 ±	0.25 ±	38.6 ±	1.55 ±	1.39 ±
		0.5	0.53	1.04	0.10	0.00	1.5	0.02**	0.06
Residue	WT	50.2 ±	6.27 ±	10.84 ±	0.82 ±	0.04 ±	18.0 ±	1.73 ±	2.86 ±
		1.8	0.71	1.09	0.06	0.00	1.7	0.02	0.13
	TR	57.9 ±	6.46 ±	9.54 ±	0.63 ±	0.03 ±	16.7 ±	1.48 ±	3.48 ±
		1.0	0.43	0.65	0.01**	0.00	1.1	0.00**	0.16**

C-Carbohydrates, G - Guaiacyl lignin, S - Syringyl lignin, H - *p*-hydroxyphenyl, P - phenolics, L - G+S+H+P, S/G - Syringyl to Guaiacyl ratio. All values are relative. Mean ± SE, *n* = 3 technical replicates. WT is combination of 6 individual trees. Trans is combination of two trees from each transgenic line (8, 4, 17). Asterisks correspond to means significantly different from WT according to the ANOVA (* *P* ≤ 0.1, ** *P* ≤ 0.05, *** *P* ≤ 0.01).